

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Article: The article addresses one of the urgent problems - transformation of higher education in the conditions of digitalization.. Achieving this goal is especially important due to the spread of cloud computing, public high-speed Internet, with the widespread introduction of smart digital tools, the use of artificial intelligence methods and the widespread introduction of virtual reality technology. Introduction of digital technologies has been studied that provides an opportunity to improve education, allowing planning concrete steps to transform the work of universities, as well as to improve educational and educational work.

Key words: digital technologies, education system, digital transformation, educational work, students, training, teacher, Internet, higher education, digitalization, digital economy, online education

Introduction.

All sectors of the economy are undergoing a digital transformation. And education is no exception, despite its inherent inertia and even ossification. According to a study by Oxford scientists Carl Frey and Michael Osborne, the professions of a teacher, coach and manager in education are not threatened with death from robotics. However, no one has canceled the digitalization of education, and it will need to adapt to it by mastering new tools and acquiring new skills. According to the forecast of Synergy University, in a couple of years new professions will become in demand on the market, such as a developer of educational

trajectories, a tutor or an architect of virtual reality. The labor market requires a qualitatively different content of graduate training. Digitalization affects not only the content of education, but also its organization [1]. These processes have mixed consequences for the positioning of both universities and teaching staff. The necessary competencies are often acquired outside the walls of educational institutions, since educational programs often do not keep up with the dynamics of technology development. The teacher turns from a carrier of the transferred knowledge and skills into a navigator who helps to navigate the knowledge bases. All these issues are particularly acute in connection with the reform of the Russian higher education system. The necessary optimization is replaced by a simple reduction in the number of universities and their financial support. The assessment of the content of scientific activity is replaced by formal details of science. Pedagogical work acquires a new character. The penetration of digital technologies (CT) into all spheres of life requires a new quality of education from the mass worker. Today, basic literacy, which is formed by the existing education system, is not enough, more than 50% of employees perform work where the necessary level of literacy can be replaced by a computer. Only 13% of them have a level of literacy that exceeds the level of intelligent computer systems (having today or expected in the next ten years). At the same time, the share of workers with a high level of general literacy has decreased compared to the nineties. The training of modern workers is inferior to the training of workers who worked two decades ago. The modern education system needs radical changes [7]. The research of scientists Kramarenko N. S., Kvashin A. Yu., Karakozov S. D., Uvarov A. Yu., Akimova O. B., showed that due to limited resources and insufficient digital literacy of educational workers, digital transformation affects educational organizations with

delay and unevenly, that the education reforms carried out in recent decades have proved to be ineffective. The digital revolution has brought with it the means to solve the challenges it faces. The productivity of intellectual labor of a person who skillfully uses digital technologies and tools in his work increases significantly. Politicians and economists often believe that a similar effect should be observed in the field of education, and the only obstacle to improving the quality of educational organizations is the technological digital gap caused by the lack of funds from the central bank. Domestic and international experience shows that the presence of CT among the participants of the educational process is a necessary, but insufficient condition for improving the effectiveness of educational and educational work [8]. The spread of CT contributes to the improvement of the work of individual creative teachers, but they are not able to increase the effectiveness of the traditionally organized educational process. Expanding access to the Internet and mobile computers (laptops, tablets, smartphones, etc.) helps to bridge the digital divide between those who have access to the Central bank and those who do not. This is a technological gap. The spread of mobile devices and the Internet is gradually eliminating the "digital divide". In the coming years, this gap will turn from a significant factor to an insignificant one. As the "technological digital divide" is being overcome, a new digital divide is growing. This is due to the inequality between those who are able to creatively use CT to perform non-standard work, such as research, observation, construction, and those who are able to use CT only for routine operations [2]. A new "digital divide" is growing in all areas where CT is being formed, among representatives of all social groups, and this begins in schools and universities. Overcoming the new digital divide is associated with updating content and is becoming one of the urgent tasks of education. Many scientists agree

that today the computer is becoming the first universal mass tool for working with all types of information [6]. Modern computer programs allow you to work in a new way with images, sound, video materials and texts, with calculations, with information models of various objects, etc. [3]. In the coming years, employees of the Department of Education and methodologists will have to change their traditional views on learning outcomes, taking into account the mass distribution of new digital information tools. They will have to review the solutions used to verify the achievement of the required educational results and determine the content of general education. In the context of our research, one of the obvious solutions is the development and implementation of an electronic information and educational environment (EIOS) in the educational process of an educational institution. EIOS is a necessary component designed to ensure a modern educational process. EIOS should use modern technological platforms to implement the flow of knowledge, allowing all participants to effectively interact in the educational process through synchronous and asynchronous communication. With the correct construction of the educational process with the help of EIOS, the advantages of this innovation are obvious. We will list just a few of them. 1. Minimization of existing "technological gaps". 2. EIOS allows us to successfully solve modern problems of education. 3. Personalization of the learning path. 4. It becomes possible to erase the boundaries of time and space. Introduction to EIOS allows you to study regardless of the location of the teacher and the student: training can be anywhere, at any time. The location of the teacher and the student is no longer so important, it is enough to have a "guide" to the world of knowledge. Maikop State Technological University is actively engaged in the process of transition to a mixed mode of education, implemented in the educational program of the University, is working on improving

the EIOS of the University. A unified information and educational space of the university has been created, including a secondary education portal, a schedule of classes on mobile applications, an electronic portfolio and an online rating system [4]. EIOS helps to effectively monitor the academic work of each student. The range of his possible actions increases, at the same time his responsibility for the effectiveness of educational work increases. The widespread use of multimedia educational materials developed taking into account the requirements of pedagogical design largely removes the responsibility for "delivering educational content" from teachers, allowing them to concentrate on pedagogical support of students, organizational, pedagogical and educational work. Data centers are rapidly distributed and updated (high-speed Internet; high-performance digital mobile devices-smartphones, tablets, etc.; Web 2.0 tools – blogs, wikis, social networks, etc.; cloud services-Google, Office 365, etc.; a new generation of virtual reality and artificial intelligence devices. This opens up unlimited access to digital tools, materials and services. Students and teachers gain unprecedented control over their information space and its sharing. Their opportunities for self-control and mutual control, for the formation of interest in learning, for meaningful learning have expanded. It is quite obvious that many competing sources are available to students and teachers: digital educational resources, training programs, online courses and various online services, including EIOS. Digital sources available via the Internet number hundreds of thousands of educational materials, thanks to them there is a real opportunity to select educational materials taking into account the individual characteristics and needs of students, to differentiate their educational work, to achieve the full achievement of the required educational results by each of them. The main means of fixing the content of education in an educational institution should

be the requirements for educational results – the standards of educational achievements. The members of the scientific and pedagogical team should determine and approve them for each subject area, taking into account the current standard on education, regional standards and local conditions. The results of training are formally recorded in the training programs, are not always known and understood by the trainees, are poorly correlated with the tasks that are offered during the certification. The educational results of various disciplines do not always agree both on the content and on the planned time of their achievement. Their description, as a rule, is not operationalized. As a result, they do not have a noticeable impact on the selection of educational material. It is necessary to switch to the use of pedagogical design procedures, to review the practice of planning educational work. The use of a digital information environment helps this [5]. It should be noted that digital technologies provide a lot of opportunities for improving education, but their integration into the educational process is far from easy. By itself, equipping educational organizations with CT does not lead to an increase in educational results. The digital transformation of education can be imagined as a solution to the problems of bridging the digital divide.

Reference:

1. Akimova O. B., Shcherbin M. D. Digital transformation of education: timeliness of educational and cognitive independence of students // Innovative projects and programs in education. 2018. No. 1. pp. 27-34.
2. Podtserob M. We will have to change [Electronic resource] // Vedomosti. 2017. No. 4342. URL: <https://www.vedomosti.ru/management/articles/2017/06/15/694456-rinok-truda>
3. Kozlova N. S. The relevance of information security in the banking system// Actual problems of technical sciences: collection of articles of the International Scientific and Practical Conference. Ufa, 2015. pp. 105-108.
4. Kozlova N. S. The relevance of online education for IT specialists/ / Bulletin of the Maikop State Technological University. 2018. Issue 4. pp. 80-85.
5. Kozlova N. S. Actual issues of personnel support for IT specialists in the period of digital transformation / / Digital economy: a new reality: a collection of articles on the results of the International scientific and practical videoconference dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the university. Maykop, 2018. pp. 45-48.
6. Kozlova N. S. Modern technologies in network security / / Digital economy: a new reality: a collection of articles on the results of the International scientific and practical videoconference dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the university. Maykop, 2018. pp. 93-97.